
THE GLORIFICATION OF THE TURKISH LANGUAGE IN THE WORK "MUHOKAMAT UL-LUGHATAYN".

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7848010>

Abdimominova Dildora

2nd stage student of Uzbek philology at TerDU

Annotation.

"In this article, the work "Muhokamat ul-lughatayn" by the thinker Alisher Navoi, the sultan of the word property, is commented, and his views on linguistics and literary studies.

Key words.

Holy Quran, rhyming, Huna, Kilchakin, Turkish, Persian, Vov, Yoy, Ter, Telmurmak phonetic, Hijri, Milodi, Motabar, lexicography, linguistics, morphology, lexicon

It is known to the whole Uzbek people that our great grandfather Alisher Navoi has works related to literature such as "Khamsa", "Lison ut-tayr", but the Sultan of words is a skilled writer who has created effectively not only in art, but also in the fields of linguistics and lexicography. As a vivid example of this, we can take the work "Muhokamat ul-lughatayn". Navoi not only contributed to the development of the Turkish language by creating a masterpiece, but also developed its development theoretically. "Muhokamat ul-lug'atayn" is a work created in 905 Hijri, 1499 AD, which shows that the Turkish language has a rich and broad potential compared to the Sort language, while comparing the Turkish and Persian languages. This work also begins with praise to Allah in accordance with the traditions of the literature of the Muslim East. After that, he proved that the world was created with words, that the Arabic language is superior to all other languages, that our prophet Muhammad (pbuh) spoke in it, and that the Holy Qur'an was revealed in that language is an honorable aspect of this language. Turkish Rubai quotes. In the work, he considers 3 languages as the "original and reliable" languages after Arabic, Turkish, Persian, and Hindi, and says that the origin of these languages is related to the children of Prophet Noah.

In his work, Navoi combines Turkish and Persian, which he knows perfectly, and explains the linguistic and poetic aspects of the two languages. The work mainly compares the phonetics, lexicon and morphology of the two languages. During the study of Asra, we can witness the fact that the number of vowels in the

Persian language is limited, and in the Uzbek language, it is distinguished by its length and length. Also, the ease of the Turkish language compared to Persian is shown by the presence of rhyming words. The letters "vov" - "y" and "yoy" - "d" in the phonetics of the Persian language "vov" - "o" and "u"; "yoy" gives the sounds "i" and "e", and in the Turkish language, it shows that these 2 letters express each 3 or 4 sounds through a single word "ter". This word has the meanings termok, may, ôq, and the difference of "yoy" in the word "sweat" according to the meaning of pronunciation, but expressing the same appearance in the writing, creates the phonetic possibilities of the Turkish language. The rich opportunity of the Uzbeks is given in the composition of the work by the natural landscape, household items, hunting process, many species of animals and birds, and the fact that there is no alternative in Persian, they use mostly the words of the Uzbeks. proves through For example, according to the gender of the deer hunted by the Turkish people, the male is called "Huna" and the female is "Kilchakin", while in Persian they hardly distinguish between them, they only name some parts of the sheep, but the bones, marrow, back parts of the ribs of the sheep. says that it is mainly expressed in Turkish. Among the words that have been adopted from Turkish to Persian, there are words such as kaymak, kathama, kurut, uloba, bulama, kuymiq. In his work, Navoi lists 100 verbs that do not have equivalents in Persian. In particular, in the comment given to the word "termulmak" in the work, it is noted that this word does not exist in Persian, and when the eyes of the beloved touch the lover's face, the lover's "the age of the telmurmagi of the request" is worthy of the following verse: When your eyes are always watching my blood, Who, no matter how many times you look at me, you will not be far away. Alisher Navoi reflects the richness of the Turkish language with another example, that is, in terms of peace and multi-meaning of words, and through these words, the abundance of words in Turkish compared to Persian, which is the basis for allusion and tajnis art in poetic art, and It illuminates the unique features of the tuyuk genre, which is created through tajnis and is not used in Persian poetry, through examples. The fact that this work is important not only for linguistics, but also for literature and literary studies shows that Navoi is the owner of great skill. In the composition of the work, our grandfather not only compares the differences between the words between the two languages, but mentions with deep respect the mature figures of the literature created in the Persian language. read and gave information about the mutual cooperation of poets in two languages, literary discussions, discussions, and artistic evenings. Navoi makes a reasonable analysis of the wealth and power of the Uzbek

language, and comes to the following conclusion: "They remained hidden because they didn't think about it... the unskilled young men are busy reciting poems with easy words." For this reason, Navoi encourages Uzbek poets to create in the Uzbek language. There are 4 manuscripts of the work in science, these are; 1. The copy stored in the Revan Library of the Topqopi Palace Museum in Istanbul, which includes other works of the poet, is considered to be kept under inventory number 808 and is cited on its pages 774a-781b; 2. A copy of pages 773b-781a kept under inventory number 4056 in the Fatih section of the Suleymaniye Library in Istanbul; 3. The Paris copy is preserved under inventory number Suppl.Turc.317|1513 and occupies pages 277b-285b; 4. Budapest copy. In the work, the poet revealed through examples that the conveniences, opportunities and vocabulary of the Turkish language are higher than those of the Persian language. Also, it is noteworthy that this work, like the rest of Navoi's works, begins with the Eastern tradition, that is, praise to God. This work is a scientific work, and the wide possibilities of the Uzbek language are fully explained in the work. One of the important tasks of linguists and literary scholars is to teach Navoi's works to young people and promote the poet's creativity.

REFERENCES:

1. Sh. Sirojiddinov, D. Yusupova, O. Davlatov - "Navoiyshunoslik". Tashkent. Civilization-2018